

APPLICATIONS OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES IN GAS TURBINE AERO ENGINES

C. Ruffles
ROLLS-ROYCE plc
ENGLAND

ABSTRACT

There has been major use of composites in gas turbine engines since the early 1960s, when parts such as the compressor system in Rolls-Royce RB108 were manufactured in glass reinforced plastic.

This paper describes conventional composite materials which offer the designer the potential of strength and high stiffness with light weight. Metal and Ceramic matrix composites extend this possibility to the highest temperature parts of the engine.

Current and future composite applications in Rolls-Royce aero engines will be described along with the limitations to the rate of progress.

1.0 Introduction

It is almost exactly fifty years since composite materials were first used in major aerospace structures. As a response to the threatened shortage of aluminium, Supermarine built an all composite Spitfire using Aerolite (now Ciba Geigy) phenolic resin reinforced with flax. The airframe was quite successful but never saw production since adequate supplies of aluminium were maintained throughout the war.

The 1950s were years of consolidation in composites as the general understanding of glass reinforcement was developed and more exotic fibres, such as boron, were considered. By the early 1960s glass fibre reinforced plastics had matured to the point that they were serious contenders for aerospace applications and carbon fibres were looking practical. Carbon offered the possibility of four times the modulus and twice the strength of comparable glass composites in a form that allowed practical processing and manufacturing techniques.

Figure 1 RB162 composite compressor casing and stator assembly

VML 57960

In parallel with these material developments, Rolls-Royce was designing a family of lift engines intended for the first generation vertical take-off aircraft. The drive for high thrust:weight ratios (10:1) forced the designers to consider the potential of composite materials. The RB108 of the early '60s used glass composites for the compressor casing, stators and rotor blades. This engine evolved to become the RB162, still with the composite compressor. The RB162 eventually saw service, albeit rotated through 90 degrees, as the boost engine in the deHavilland Trident IIIB airliner. It is still the only engine to have entered service with a composite compressor system. By the end of the decade the Rolls-Royce Conway was in civilian service in the VC10 with a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy fan blade.

Figure 2 RB162 composite-bladed rotor assembly

VML 57961

The introduction of the "big-fan" engines in the early 1970s coincided with the wide spread availability of carbon fibre-epoxy composites.

One of the most publicised uses of composites around this time was on the Hyfil fan blade which afforded important performance and weight advantages. To make each blade vast numbers of the

carbon fibres were bonded by resin adhesive into thin flat plies which after being cut to shape were stacked in a pile and bonded into one solid mass. The blades were smooth, black and amazingly strong and light.

However, on engine testing, the blade proved unable to withstand the sudden impact on the thin leading edge of simulated bird strike conditions. The back up titanium fan therefore replaced the Hyfil constructions.

In size, the nacelles for these engines represented a step change from the previous generation. The weight of these structures necessitated the use of light materials and by the end of the 1970s the nacelle and their associated systems included major composite elements. Since then there has been a gradual increase in the use of composites in the nacelle to the point that carbon fibre - epoxy now represents half the volume of the structure.

Figure 3 Carbon fan

HB 239.12

2.0 Why Composites ?

Composite materials are now well established in many industries, often to the point that they have become the "natural" material to use. Each of these industries seeks its own specific advantages from the materials.

The factors that drive aerospace to composites are the high specific stiffness and strength together with an increasing tendency to offer a cost advantage. Weight is a primary consideration in any aerospace structure and the ability to produce light but extremely stiff and strong components has seen a rise in the use of composites in both airframes and engines.

Figure 4 Impact of improved thrust to weight ratio on Civil engines

ETG 36381 VC Issue 1

In engines, polymer matrix composites (PMC) are often competing against titanium, and systems such as carbon-epoxy are able to show significant cost savings in the finished part. Metal matrix

composites (MMC) are potentially attractive where temperatures are too high for PMCs and for very high temperature where loads are moderate ceramic matrix composites (CMC) hold out exciting possibilities. CMCs are conceptually different from polymer and metal composites as they are not generally fibre reinforced but rather fibre toughened, since the fibres modify the crack propagation properties of the material.

Neither MMC nor CMC systems approach the maturity of polymer composites and neither is yet in large scale production at a cost that allows their economical application.

Figure 5 RB211 Cowl door in carbon fibre epoxy composite

VML 57952

3.0 Composites Today

The current generation of large, civil gas turbine engines incorporate substantial amounts of composite materials. Most of this will be in the nacelle. With the exception of the fan and the nozzle, virtually all of a modern aero engine that is viewed externally is carbon fibre. Very little composite is used in the core engine other than simple parts such as fairings. Nevertheless, composites represent something of the order of ten percent of the weight of a turbo-fan powerplant.

The generation of engine due to enter service in the mid 1990s, typified by the Rolls-Royce Trent, extends the application of composites into the engine core. Fan outlet guide vanes offer substantial savings in weight and cost relative to the metal parts. Although at first sight these seem to be simple aerofoils, the primary design requirement is that they should not flutter. There is a complex compromise to be reached to define a vane that is stiff enough, can be economically manufactured in large numbers and where the construction is amenable to the available methods of analysis so that satisfactory dynamic behaviour can be demonstrated before the component is committed to manufacture.

On smaller engines, such as the Rolls-Royce Tay, the bypass duct is a sophisticated composite structure. Developments of the Tay and its successor, the BMW-RR 700 series, use the duct as a structural member supporting the engine in the airframe. Testing has demonstrated this to be an entirely satisfactory arrangement and edges composites further into the realm of structural parts.

4.0 The Future

As far as aero gas turbines are concerned, composites stand at something of a crossroads. If the use of polymer composites is to be extended then they must move into the core of the engine and find application as main, structural components which will be critical to the successful operation of the engine. Civil engine demonstrator programmes at Rolls-Royce are already developing major carbon fibre components such as the fan case and fan bearing support structure. If structural fan outlet guide vanes are included in RB 211 derivatives, then the whole plane defined by the bearing structure - OGV - fan case can potentially be in composite. In metal, these parts represent some ten percent of the total weight of the engine.

The front bearing structure represents a convenient split between the necessary classes of resin systems. Any parts up to and including the fan or round the outside of the low pressure system is a candidate for carbon (or glass) reinforced epoxies with a temperature capability of 150-160 C. The pressure rise and consequent increase in temperature through the fan means that anything aft of the fan will require a resin system in the PMF-15 class ie. 250-270 C. It is not only the core air temperatures that must be considered but also the high pressure (hence high temperature) air circulated within the internal air system of the engine. Further, any composites washed by oil or carrying oil system pipes will be subjected to high temperatures. As the pressure ratios rise in the three shaft configuration of the RB211/Trent family, the structural casing between the intermediate and high pressure compressors is becoming just out of reach of even the latest generation of high temperature resins.

The military engine offers a different set of opportunities. In general, these do not have a nacelle in the sense of the civil engine because they tend to be installed within the airframe. As a result they have not made the same use of composites that is seen on civil engines. However, the different style of the military engine allows consideration of a carbon fibre reinforced polymer intermediate casing and this is already under development as part of a demonstrator programme.

Military demonstrators also offer applications for both MMC and CMC components. MMCs offer attractive possibilities in compressor rotors where a relatively thin ring of silicon carbide fibre reinforced titanium under the blade rim can replace the conventional and heavy central cob and diaphragm. Preliminary versions of such compressors have already run and there is a combined European programme to develop the second generation.

Figure 6 Experimental silicon carbide fibre reinforced titanium bladed-ring. Diameter = 140mm

VML 57954

CMCs are particularly applicable to the exhaust and reheat sections of a military engine where their low density and high temperature capability can be exploited in spite of their relatively low strength and toughness. Weight at the extreme rear of a modern combat aircraft is critical and has important knock-on effect on the aerodynamics and structure of the airframe itself. The high temperature ability of CMC materials allows the internal cooling flows to be reduced with corresponding benefits to the engine performance. Reheat and combustor parts have already run in development and demonstrator engines while an exhaust unit and nozzle vane are currently under development.

Figure 7 Ceramic exhaust nozzle petals and their application on a military engine

ETG 36379V Issue 1

In the long term, estimated economic development will lead to a growth in the size of subsonic aircraft. This growth and the likely increase in fuel price will lead to the development of higher bypass ratio engines. Increases in fan diameter on a given core offer a challenging route to lower sfc. The higher bypass ratios given by larger fans inevitably means increasing nacelle size and weight. The theoretically attractive sfc improvements can easily be offset by the installation penalties of increased weight and drag. In fact, studies have shown that for bypass ratios of up to 12, direct drive three shaft engines still have the advantage. For example the below pylon weight of this size of engine would increase by approximately 45% relative to today's engines with bypass ratios of 6. The geared engines studied show increases of over 50%. This is coupled with a predicted increase of 1% in fuel burn for geared engines compared with no change for direct drive engines. The result is that achievement of the best aircraft operating economics does not necessarily go with increasing bypass ratio. Nevertheless, a modest increase in bypass ratios from today's 6.0 to circa 9.0 using a direct drive 3 shaft engine concept, can yield benefits in take-off performance and perhaps noise and fuel burn.

Obviously the integration of composites into these engines, particularly in the primary load paths, will yield further benefits in fuel burn and payload range. However, the benefits of these two factors are diminishing. The major driving factor for future civil engines will be the cost of ownership of which a low manufacturing cost appears at the beginning of the chain. An improved design and manufacturing process for these materials is therefore essential. In military engines however, improved performance will continue to be the major market driver.

Figure 8 Composite thrust reverser components

VML 57956

5.0 Challenges in product definition

The one factor that inhibits the advancement of composites more than any other is the perceived difficulty in designing with them. One of the advantages of composites is the ability to tailor the properties of the section to accommodate the principal load directions. This advantage, however, is also the primary disadvantage since the properties now depend upon the direction and conventional "metal" approaches no longer apply. Not only are the "in-plane" properties directional but those in the "through thickness" direction (which will normally not be reinforced) are different again. In a typical carbon - epoxy system the modulus of the fibre will approach two orders of magnitude greater than that of the matrix.

Up until now the relative simplicity of the parts and their manufacturing processes has allowed the difficulties of the analysis to, at least in part, be overcome by a trial and error approach. The complexity and cost of new parts and their tooling render this unacceptable for the structural components of the future.

Figure 9 The Reality - Key technical issues that must be considered

ETG 36389V ISSUE 1

Almost all practical designs are ultimately driven by stiffness rather than by strength. In practice this means that any design that controls deflections under the limit load will almost certainly exhibit adequate strength under ultimate loads and will normally operate below the fatigue limit. This is fortuitous since design methodology is most reliable for stiffness so both deflection and dynamic response can be modelled with an acceptable degree of accuracy. Composites are often thought of as brittle, yet, particularly in the case of PMCs, they can exhibit substantial deflection before failure - consider the pole vaulter's pole. Unlike ductile metallic materials they do not show significant plastic deformation prior to failure. The metal designer will be bewildered by the loss of his plastic safety net while the composite designer will point out that his materials retains usable properties almost up to the point of ultimate failure. In practice, composites do possess a form of "pseudo plasticity" close to final failure. The complexity of the fibre architecture results in a high degree of redundancy within the structure giving it the ability to redistribute loads as fibres fail. This property tends not to be demonstrated by small scale coupons since their relative simplicity denies the structure its internal redundancy.

Effective design with composites can only be achieved with a commitment to and understanding of composite engineering. Recent examples such as racing cars and yachts, military and light aircraft demonstrate that once this happens composites can become the "natural" material for many applications.

6.0 Conclusions

Composite materials have been in service in aero gas turbines for more than 20 years. They are now at a critical stage where, if they are to progress within the engine, they must find application in significant, structural components.

There is no doubt that polymer, metal and ceramic matrix materials will continue to erode that position of metals. In military engines, the weight and performance benefits will continue to be paramount. On the civil side, with diminishing returns on fuel burn, cost will become the driver. As the materials systems themselves develop, more challenging applications will become possible.

The limitation on the rate of progress of composites is the ability to engineer them with confidence and to accurately predict their behaviour so that the vision is made possible. This will clearly improve as more composites are used. A growing understanding of and sympathy for the materials combined with the flair of the designer will bring about innovative applications for composites.

7.0 Acknowledgement

The author would like to thank Rolls-Royce plc for permission to publish this paper, to Dr. J. Dominy for assistance in writing the paper and to Mr. C. J. B. Barkey for assistance in its production.